

COcyber Cybersphere Insights – Special Edition

National Case Studies on Cybersecurity Technology and Information Transfer

Setting the scene

This Cybersphere Insights Special Edition presents findings from [COcyber's Deliverable D4.2 National Case Studies Booklet on Cybersecurity Technology and Information Transfer](#). The report offers a **consolidated overview of the cybersecurity landscapes of Lithuania, Spain, Hungary, and Slovenia**, focusing on how each country organises technology transfer, supports the development of cybersecurity capabilities, and structures national mechanisms for sharing information and managing dual-use innovation.

Led by **AMETIC**, together with the national partners responsible for the country case studies – **INFOBALT (Lithuania)**, **IVSZ (Hungary)**, **AMETIC (Spain)** and **CCIS (Slovenia)**– the deliverable brings together the key national characteristics that shape governance, institutional maturity, innovation ecosystems, and operational practices in these Member States.

[Read the full deliverable](#)

Country Case Studies

Lithuania

Lithuania demonstrates a centralised cybersecurity model led by the Ministry of Defence and the National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC). A modernised Cybersecurity Law, active CERT structures, and growing R&D initiatives position the country as a strong EU-aligned actor. Technology transfer is supported through defence-innovation programmes, GovTech initiatives, and national innovation agencies, though progress is slowed by administrative burdens, fragmented coordination, and limited prototyping resources.

The graphic features a dark background with abstract blue and green light patterns. In the top left is the coccyber logo. The word "Lithuania" is written in large white font. To the right is the Lithuanian flag. Below the title is a paragraph of text. At the bottom left are logos for the European Union and ECCC. At the bottom right is the URL coccyber.eu.

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Lithuania

Lithuania's case study examines how its NCSC-centred cybersecurity system functions, detailing national governance arrangements, defence-linked technology-transfer programmes, information-sharing systems, & the approach to deploying dual-use cybersecurity technologies.

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Information sharing is structured and supported by national systems (CSIS, MISP, CERTs), but legal constraints, uneven maturity, and trust gaps still affect operational effectiveness. Dual-use development is advancing through defence-linked innovation, yet licensing complexity, export controls, and limited scaling pathways remain key obstacles.

[Check the Lithuanian case study](#)

Spain

Spain operates within a mature and comprehensive cybersecurity framework anchored in the National Cybersecurity Strategy (2019) and the National Cybersecurity Plan (2022–2025). These structures support coordination, innovation, and international engagement, although implementation is affected by regional fragmentation, talent shortages, and SME vulnerabilities.

The graphic features a dark background with abstract blue and green light streaks. In the top left is the coccyber logo. The word "Spain" is written in large white font. To the right is the flag of Spain. Below the title is a paragraph of text. At the bottom left are logos for the European Union and ECCC. At the bottom right is the URL coccyber.eu.

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Spain

Spain's case study evaluates how effectively the country transfers cybersecurity technologies & shares threat intelligence, examining governance structures, technology-transfer mechanisms, information-sharing practices, & the national landscape for dual-use cybersecurity deployment.

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Technology transfer benefits from strong national instruments (INCIBE's PPI, CDTI programmes), but bureaucratic barriers, IPR uncertainties, and preference for foreign solutions continue to impede adoption. Spain's information-sharing system—led by CCN-CERT, INCIBE-CERT, and the National SOC Network—is robust, though mistrust, legal constraints, and uneven reporting reduce its full effectiveness. Dual-use technology deployment is recognised as strategically important but slowed by licensing timelines, restrictive IPR rules, and ethical considerations.

[Check the Spanish case study](#)

Hungary

Hungary's cybersecurity environment is shaped by a state-centred governance model and an early but uniquely national transposition of NIS2. This model consolidates regulatory authority but introduces differences from other EU Member States that affect supervisory practices and cross-sector alignment.

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Hungary

Hungary's case study evaluates how its state-centred cybersecurity system supports technology transfer and information sharing, examining governance structures, public-sector innovation pathways, cross-sector information-sharing practices, and the role of defence-led dual-use development

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Technology transfer remains uneven: strong public-sector capabilities contrast with persistent institutional fragmentation, limited private-sector engagement, and gaps in innovation-to-market pathways. Information-sharing mechanisms function reliably within government structures but show weaker performance across sectors, owing to varying maturity levels, trust issues, and legal uncertainties. Dual-use technologies are primarily framed through a defence lens, which narrows opportunities for broader civilian innovation and commercialisation.

[Check the Hungarian case study](#)

Slovenia

Slovenia continues to develop its national cybersecurity system through updated legislation, institutional restructuring, and emerging collaborations. Its governance model includes URSIV, SI-CERT, SIGOV-CERT, and sectoral bodies, but coordination gaps, unclear responsibilities, and resource constraints reduce system cohesion.

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Slovenia

Slovenia's case study examines how the country's EU-aligned cybersecurity framework operates in practice, detailing its institutional setup, technology-transfer landscape, information-sharing arrangements, and the gradual evolution of its dual-use cybersecurity capabilities.

cocyper.eu

Technology transfer is supported by research organisations and innovation actors, yet lacks strong incentives, clear institutional linkages, and sustained financial support to scale outcomes. Information sharing is present through CERT structures and sectoral bridges, though uneven maturity, limited trust, and the absence of a fully centralised intelligence hub constrain effectiveness. Dual-use cybersecurity remains a recognised priority, but operational frameworks and incentives for practical deployment are still emerging.

[Check the Slovenian case study](#)

Final Remarks

Across all four Member States, COcyber's analysis identifies a **shared need for stronger and more coherent governance structures, improved trust-based information**

sharing, clearer and harmonised regulatory pathways, and more supportive innovation ecosystems. Addressing these systemic gaps is essential to enhance Europe's collective cybersecurity resilience and ensure that civilian and defence sectors can jointly respond to evolving threats.

⚡ Don't miss any future COcyber events connecting the dots between civilian and defence cyber security initiatives. Join our community now at <https://cocyber.eu/user/register>

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